

**Forest Dependence and its Degradation in Meghalaya:
*The Potential Reasons***

Utpal K. De¹

Abstract

Interlinkages among population, poverty and deforestation are crucial for examination amid growing population, incidence of poverty and degradation of forests. Several studies have identified the primary reasons for the loss of forest cover as population growth, commercial logging and the spread of cattle ranches. This paper tries to unfold the nature of dependence on forest, and factors causing its degradation in Meghalaya in an interlinking fashion drawn through correlation, regression and intersectoral flow analysis. The analysis reveals that family size, incidence of poverty, cultivation practice, remoteness of the area and consumption or livelihood pattern have important impact on the extraction of forest resources. Education helps in conservation and sustainable use of the forest resources. Broadly, there is important inter-linkage between population growth, incidence of poverty and degradation of forest in the region. The emerging policy implication is that the best way to preserve forest is to control population growth, reduce poverty, improve economy through education and technological development, and follow a judicious land use pattern so as to maintain the forest resource and its productivity, which in turn provide sustainable livelihood.

Keywords: Forest dependence, Degradation of forest, Factors of degradation, Meghalaya

¹ Professor, Department of Economics, North-Eastern Hill University (NEHU), Shillong, India. Email: utpalkde@gmail.com.

Background

The population, poverty and the degradation of forests interlinkages have been debated for long period of time. In the context of forests, population growth has often been blamed for the loss of forest cover (Southgate, 1988; Ives and Messerli, 1988; FAO, 1993; Gill, 1999 Ehrlich and Ehrlich, 1990; Mink, 1993; Dasgupta, 1994) or it is commercial extraction, including the spread of cattle rearing activities (Engelman, 1997).

Majority of people in North-East India and particularly in Meghalaya still depend directly on land-based subsistence production. The population, poverty and environment interrelationship could hardly be direct since, poor standard of living of the rural population intensify pressure on natural resources like forests, which in turn aggravate poverty due to fall in productive capacity.

In the same way, population growth and environmental (here forest) degradation is both cause and consequence of poverty (Duraiappah, 1996). Population growth cause significant impact on natural resources when it exceeds carrying capacity of the resource base that is highly inelastic in supply like forest to a certain extent. The impact on the environment is often viewed in terms of carrying capacity, and that is usually related to the availability of a limiting resource (Reidhead, et al., 1997).

Increasing production targets to meet growing need of population should not degrade a resource base beyond its regenerative capacity. The population-environment causal relationship is both-way. People modify their environment, and in turn, they are affected by changes in the environmental conditions. While these interrelationships unfold over time, the socio-economic context plays an important role in mediating them. In a similar fashion, socio-political and economic factors cause overall changes of the environment.

The poverty-environment linkage is often looked as a vicious circle between poverty and environmental degradation (De, 2006). Due to rapid population growth, poverty increases that causes expansion of cultivation to less productive lands, which intensifies poverty further (Malthus, 1798). Existing literature offers two major viewpoints about the precise relationships between population growth and environmental changes.

Majority of the population in Meghalaya still live-in rural areas and agriculture is their main occupation (Government of Meghalaya, 2017). The cultivable area have been extended to support the growing population and improve the economic conditions of rural population (Husain, 1994). It has been extended even to the steep hill slopes and clearing of forests have taken place that has caused rising intensity of soil erosion.

Also, pressure on forest has been compounded for the extensive practice of shifting cultivation (Lyngkhoi, 2007; De, 2003). Also, demand for timber and non-timber forest products has been increasing, as revealed from the rising contribution of the forest resources to net state domestic product (NSDP) of Meghalaya. Not only the deforestation has been taking place for the expansion of agriculture, but also due to collection of fuel-wood that is much needed in the rural set-up.

For the unbridled population growth, unsustainable land use pattern and consumerism, the forest resources base of the region have been shrinking rapidly. The degradation of forest cover contributes to poverty by deteriorating the productivity of forests, on which the poor people rely the most, and rising poverty forces them to undertake more unsustainable practices, which causes further damage to the environment (Neena, 2000).

Sustainable development is not just about protecting the environment but it is about how we can make the best productive use of natural resources in order to eliminate poverty and improve quality of life (Aluko, 2004). A multidisciplinary approach is

required to understand the process of environmental degradation that has contributed to the incidence of poverty causing further degradation in Meghalaya.

Forest is the primary source of small timber, fuel, fodder, grazing, and a variety of other minor forest produce such as grass, fencing material, bark, fibre, edible flowers and roots, gum and honey. Many of these forest products have commercial and industrial importance (Chauhan and Chuahan, 1998). However, the exploitation of forest resources in Meghalaya has not been successful in alleviating poverty significantly. Rather, the uncontrolled exploitation of forest resources owing to its nature of being open access has put the rural people under vicious circle.

The paper examined the nature of population, poverty and degradation of forest interlinkages. Also, impacts of various factors on the deforestation in Meghalaya have been examined. The next section provides a brief review of relevant literature, which is followed by a description of data and methodology. Thereafter findings of the analysis is presented. The last section provides policy implications.

Studies on the Linkages

Ehrlich (1968), Meadows et al. (1972), Ehrlich and Ehrlich (1990), warned the world community with their prediction of possible short-fall of critical natural resources for the ceaseless population growth leading to break down of ecosystem and the economy. The possible exhaustion of renewable natural resources like forests was predicted if the extraction rate surpassed the carrying capacity of the resource base. Keeping a parity was therefore essential between surge of population and extraction of resources for sustainable progress.

Poverty and the population growth have often been blamed to be the primary reasons for the deforestation (Dreze and

Sen, 1989; Sen, 1994; Birdsall, 1994). Poverty and population growth of more than 2% every year has adversely affected the growth and development of the Meghalaya economy (Joshi, 1990). It was also identified that the forest degradation affected the environment and available resources for economic progress. The reasons for forest degradation were also due to the institutional structure and poverty (Dasgupta, 1994).

However, the neoclassical free market economists argued in line with demographic dividend that population growth adds to the benefit (Simon, 1981, 1996; Simon and Myers, 1994). In several ways, population growth contributes to economic growth and helps better management of natural resources through knowledge expansion (Johnson, 2000). The experience of rising pollution in several parts of the world after industrial revolution, global warming, depletion of forest resources, declining productivity of soil and biodiversity in the 2nd half of previous century raised concern across the globe. These have been not only due to the population growth but also the use of modern technology to meet rising greed of the populace.

Population growth without any technological breakthrough, as long its size remains below the carrying capacity, positively helps in better resource utilization. Beyond a certain limit, it causes serious damage of resources. Technological modernization leads to rise in the scope for resource use and degradation if there is uncertainty in regeneration at the required speed (De, *op. cit*; Bhagat and Hassan, 1994).

Therefore, natural resource degradation apart from population explosion may be due to rising consumerism, which is more importantly supported by the technological advancement (Macneill, 1989). Property rights also may play its part. The mostly open forest resource of Meghalaya, which is despite community ownership, has been subject to the tragedy of commons (Hardin, 1968).

Environmental Kuznets Curve hypothesis argued that economic growth of forest dwellers would solve the degradation problem. But Cropper and Griffiths (1994) pointed out that the damages in developing countries arise due of market failure associated with lack of property right. It is because of the fact that majority of the poor people do not possess any property right and they have very little incentive to conserve, except sympathy. The suggestion is therefore to control population growth to reduce the rate of deforestation.

Despite the blame put on the poor, on several occasions it has been found that they take measures (with the help of indigenous knowledge and to earn sustainable return) for the conservation in their own interest, and in some cases, they have limited access due to lack of property right. As a result, the question of their responsibility for degradation does not hold good (De, 2003). It is the non-poor who rather has better access to such a resource; and severely damage it.

The rich people having better access to modern machinery on many occasions over-exploit for making profit (Boyce, 1994; Jaganathan, 1989), and damage the scope of survival of the poor. Thus, the logging activities cause deforestation in several parts of Asia, Africa and Amazonian region (Somanathan, 1991; Anderson, 1989; Repetto, 1990; Cropper and Griffiths, 1994; Sanchez, 1998; FAO, 2005). In Meghalaya commercial interest of the timber industries attracted people towards such activities across the communities during 1980s that led to unsustainable harvestingⁱ.

Agricultural and pastoral encroachment into the forest in the wake of population growth also causes deforestation. The development in communication also helped in accelerating such degradation activities (Goodland, 1991; Westby, 1987; Cruz and Gills, 1990).

The cause-effect relation among population, poverty, various indicators of human development and degradation of forest is also reflected from De (2004). Using panel data on degradation of forest, incidence of poverty and level as well as variation in per capita state domestic product (SDP), De (2006) found a significantly positive correlation between income and degradation. A positive relation is found here between poverty reduction and deforestation, which is exactly not in tune with EKC (Grossman and Krueger, 1995). He opined that the states of North East India were still lesser developed having lower per capita income than the national average and hence, they were on the rising phase of EKC.

Moreover, whatever poverty reduction had taken place, it was at the cost of easily accessible forest resources. Almost a similar finding was presented in case of Arunachal Pradesh (Kuri, 2005). It has been opined that rapid growth of population in the North East India is also partly due to the immigration from the neighboring countries, namely, Bangladesh and Nepal and they have been in many cases responsible for the damage of forest cover for sustenance (Singh, 1987). Datta (2000) and Dutta (2000) also blamed high rate of growth of population, lack of planning and uneconomic use of land for shifting cultivation for the loss of forest cover in vast areas of Meghalaya.

Materials and Methodology

Data Sources

For the purpose of analysis, both secondary and primary data have been used. Secondary data on population, literacy rate, earning from forest, area under forest were collected from various Census Reports and Statistical Handbook of Meghalaya. Since district-level time series data on poverty is not available, computation of

correlation between temporal changes in incidence of poverty with rate of degradation of forest or population is impossible. Thus, primary data was collected during April-June 2018 to better analyze the inter-linkages among those variables.

Sample Design and the Study Area

Primary survey was conducted in four sample villages in Meghalaya. These villages were selected purposively. Two of them were from East Khasi Hills, one was from West Khasi Hills and the rest one was on the border of two districts. They were chosen on the basis of a preliminary information on locations, characteristics and intensity of forest degradation, distance from their nearest towns and communication facilities.

The villages were Mawtawar, Laitjem, Sohiong and Mawlangkhar. Mawtawar and Laitjem were located in nearby Myllem Community and Rural Development (CRD) Block and Sohiong in Mawphlang CRD Block. Mawlangkhar belongs to the Mawthadraishan CRD Block of West Khasi Hills district. For the time and resource constraints, Jaintia and Garo Hills were not considered for the survey.

Sohiong and Mawlangkhar are situated about 30 and 20 KM away from nearest town Shillong and Nongstoin respectively. Distance of Mawtawar and Laitjem were about 5 and 12 km from their nearest city, Shillong. So, two villages were chosen within 15 km of distance from district headquarter, while two others were more than 15 km away from district headquarter. One saw-mill was in operation at Mawtawar during survey. Though previously there were five saw-mills at Laitjem, three were active and at Sohiong out of five and only two were in operation at the time of survey. Though there was a timber industry at Mawlangkhar, it was not in operation.

As per the personal records, Mawtawar and Sohiong recorded very high degree of deforestation during past few decades. Subsistence and commercial extraction practices cause degradation of a major portion of the erstwhile dense forests there and it has still been practiced due to the proximity to the commercial hubs and high incidence of poverty.

Influx of population from the remote villages compounded the problem. Due to lack of alternative opportunities, education facilities and rising pressure on *jhum* land; poor people migrate to urban informal sector lying mostly on the outskirts of the city. The degradation recorded in the other two villages, Laitjem and Mawlangkhar, has however been comparatively less despite more intensity of poverty and less available substitutes of forest products.

Forty households were selected from each village by simple random sampling method from among the list of households as the final sampling units. In total, the sample size was 160.

Collection of Data

From each household head, information on socio-demographic and economic conditions, *viz.*, family size and its composition, maximum educational attainment by any member of the family, land-ownership, occupation, monthly earning and its source, cultivation type, consumption pattern, materials used in housing, cattle owned, items collected from the forests were obtained. Also, the level of degradation of forests were noted. From the primary data, efforts were made to find the reasons for differences in dependence of people on the forest and the difference in level of degradation.

Method of Analysis

Since district-wise data on all the variables are not available for a long period of time, panel data regression analysis could not be applied. Therefore, by using secondary data, a two-way correlation table is constructed to examine the pattern of relationship among inter-district variation in population growth, rural poverty, changes in contribution of forestry to Net District Domestic Product (NDDP), changes in net earnings from the forest, variation in literacy rate. From the correlations among the variables, the dynamic linkage if exists and its nature in the state of Meghalaya was sought to be found.

From the observations on socio-economic characteristics of the sample households and their utilization of forest resources, the pattern of linkages was explained. The socio-economic status of the people is examined through their land holding, ownership of cattle, housing pattern, source of earning and its level. Also, dependence on forest is gathered from the items collected and their quantity, proportion of income comes from collection of forest resource, which is again regressed on several explanatory variables like per capita income, educational level, family size, land holding etc. to examine the impact of various factors on the dependence on forest resources that helps in understanding the reasons for forest resource degradation in the state and its spatial differences.

Both tabular and regression techniques are applied for analyzing the data. Along with correlation table, regression of collection of fuelwoods and earning from the collection of forest resources on relevant variables like education, family size, job status, distance from headquarter, presence or absence of saw-mills are conducted.

Before that, presence of multicollinearity has been checked by two-way correlation table of explanatory variables and

found no significant correlation among them except between job status and education or family size and income. The coefficient of respective explanatory variable shows the impact of that variable on the dependence of the family of forest for the respective item like fuelwood or earning and thus extraction leading to degradation.

Findings and Discussion

Secondary information reveals that the incidence of poverty in rural areas were high. Over time variation in NDDP or per capita NDDP was not significant, but could be used as an indicator of economic condition of the people and used in the analysis. More per capita NDDP of a district (for identical distribution) implies relatively less poor and vice-versa.

Inter-district variation in growth and density of population have significant inverse correlation with the growth of NDDP and per capita NDDP and significantly positive correlation with the variation in contribution of forest to NDDP and degradation of forest (Table 1). Variation in growth of literacy rate and per capita NDDP are negatively correlated to contribution of forest to NDDP as well as deforestation. There is a positive correlation among the proportion of family and area of *jhum* cultivation and contribution of forest to NDDP.

The results thus reveal that population growth and its rising density adversely affect and are impacted by the growing NDDP i.e., positively associated with the incidence of poverty if there is resource constraint. Even though other natural resources like minerals are there, most of those privately owned by a few owners and thus poor people are more dependent on easily accessible open forests.

It is expected that the poor have large family size for better family earning through more extraction of forest resources

and that cause more degradation. However, educated people also avail other opportunities that reduce pressure on forest and thereby its share in NDDP as well as degradation comes down. But in Meghalaya, education is not much effective due to the chronic poverty in many rural areas.

Table 1: Two Way Correlation Table

Variable	Population Growth Rate	Rural Lit. Rate	Growth of Population Density	Growth of NDDP	Growth of PC- NDDP	Change in Contribution of Forest to NDDP	Family in Jhum Cultivation (%)	Area of Jhum Cultivation
Population Growth Rate	1							
Rural Lit. Rate	0.15	1						
Growth of Population Density	--	--	1					
Growth of NDDP	-0.51**	--	-0.49*	1				
Growth of PC- NDDP	-0.77**	0.30	-0.72**		1			
Change in Contribution of Forest to NDDP	0.53**	-0.60	0.46*	0.07	-0.92**	1		
Family in Jhum Cultivation (%)	-0.11	-0.31	-0.09	0.43	-0.28	0.45*	1	
Area of Jhum Cultivation	-0.17	-0.43	-0.24	0.06	-0.35	0.48*	0.67**	1
Degradation of Forest Land	0.41*	-0.27	0.30	-0.31	-0.51**	0.46*	-0.52**	-0.05

Notes:
 (i) ** and * indicate that the correlation is significant at 1% and 5% level of significance by two-tailed test.
 (ii) Variation in rural poverty was not considered, as district-wise time series figures were not available.

Source: Compiled from the data available from Secondary sources viz. Census of India, Planning Commission and Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Government of Meghalaya.

District level variability in growth of per capita NDDP has inverse impact on the share of forest to total NDDP or deforestation. It shows that with the growth of economy, pressure on forest

reduces. However, growth of per capita NDDP of all the districts has been much lower as compared to the all-India average as observed from the decline in ranking in human poverty index. Therefore, impact on proportion of family engaged and area under *jhum* cultivation is not highly significant. With rising income, peoples' dependence on forest for food, fodder and degradation is likely decline. However, if the share of forest in NDDP rises, NDDP would have accelerated growth leading to faster degradation.

Proportion of family and area under *jhum* cultivation are found to be inversely related to the variation in degradation of forests. Even now many families especially in rural areas of some districts are dependent on *jhum* cultivation (owing to low earning and other available opportunities) and also that population density in those districts is much lower than that of other districts of East Khasi Hills, where comparatively lesser proportion of population are dependent on *jhum* and per capita availability of land is also very less.

Due to less availability of per capita forestland, cycle of fallow period is short and hence more degradation is observed. The district with higher proportion of people in *jhum*, for relatively more per capita availability of land, fallow period is longer enough to maintain higher productivity and slower degradation.

However, despite education, due to lack of availability, one cannot avail modern techniques of settled cultivation, but he may try to judiciously manage the cultivable area. It may help in controlling deforestation substantially. Again, the population growth may cause imbalances in the use of forestland for survival. With identical population growth, if quality of forest is better in a district, its contribution to per capita NDDP would be higher and hence the growth.

Analysis of the Linkage on the Basis of Primary Data

Socio-Economic Profile of Sample Villages

Household size is an important variable in the context of extraction of forest resources. Here, the family size varied between 6 and 8 (Table 2). Mawtawar recorded the lowest average family size and number of children among the four sample villages, which showed the influence of educational and healthcare facilities in neighbouring urban area. The far interior Mawlangkhar village recorded the highest family size.

Table 2: Family Structure in Four Sample Villages

Village	Persons	Males	Females	Adult	Children
Laitjem	6.82	3.30	3.55	3.62	3.20
Mawtawar	6.07	3.13	3.00	3.48	2.57
Sohiong	7.30	3.70	3.60	3.65	3.65
Mawlangkhar	8.35	4.82	4.52	4.77	3.58

Source: Compiled from the field survey

Table 3: Distribution of Households in Terms of Education of Head of Households (%)

Village	Illiterate	Literate			
		Literate but < Secondary	Secondary but < H.S.	H.S. but < Graduate	Graduate and Above
Laitjem	67.5	25.00	5.00	0.00	2.50
Mawtawar	47.5	40.00	2.50	2.50	7.50
Sohiong	90.0	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mawlangkhar	70.0	27.50	2.50	0.00	0.00

Source: Compiled from the field survey.

Mawtawar is the most advanced among all the four villages in achieving education with 52.50% literacy, of which 40% are just literate, 5% are secondary passed and 7.5% are graduates and above (Table 3). It is followed by Laitjem with 32.50% of population literate. Mawlangkhar records 30% literacy rate of

which merely 2.5% are secondary passed, while in Sohiong only 10% of the people are literate.

Incidence of poverty as estimated by using the nationally prescribed rural poverty line for the sample villages is shown in Table 4. Almost all the families in Mawlangkhar are poor, which is followed by Laitjem and Sohiong. Only about one-third of the families in Mawtawar are poor. Despite variations in the level of education, all the three villages (except Mawtawar) are suffering from chronic poverty.

Table 4: Distribution of Households as per Poor and Non-Poor (%)

Village	Poor	Non-Poor
Laitjem	80.00	20.00
Mawtawar	32.50	67.50
Sohiong	75.00	25.00
Mawlangkhar	97.50	2.50

Source: Compiled from the field survey

Mean monthly income and expenditure of the households in the study area is significantly lower as compared to national average and varies significantly across the villages (Table 5). Mean family income per month ranges between Rs 1870.25 to Rs 3743.75. Also, monthly family expenditure is the lowest in Laitjem and it is the highest in Mawlangkhar.

A question may arise on the highest average monthly family expenditure in the most interior Mawlangkhar with 97.5% of the families being poor. Actually, for estimating total family earning, the imputed values of forest produce collected are considered. With the higher family size in Mawlangkhar, majority are engaged in collecting forest resources primarily for subsistence.

Moreover, in the expenditure, values of the items collected and consumed are also incorporated. In Mawlangkhar the harvesting and hunting in the forest is carried out mainly for

subsistence, whereas in Mawtawar extracted resource is used for both subsistence and commercial purposes.

Table 5: Average Monthly Per Capita Income and Expenditure of the Sample Households (Rs.)

Village	Per Capita Income	Per Capita Expenditure	Coefficient of Variation in family income
Laitjem	623.60	498.62	99.11
Mawtawar	1232.76	476.90	95.79
Sohiong	670.17	500.93	87.99
Mawlangkhar	447.00	446.69	48.51

Source: Compiled from the field survey.

Though average family expenditure is the highest, per capita monthly expenditure is the lowest in Mawlangkhar, which is highest in Mawtawar. This is because of the larger family size in Mawlangkhar as compared to that of Mawtawar. Moreover, coefficient of variation in income is the highest in Laitjem (99.11) and lowest in Mawlangkhar (48.51). So, higher income area has a tendency to be associated with greater inequality in the distribution of income.

Most families in all four villages are engaged in agriculture and cattle rearing except a few in Mawtawar, who are in non-agricultural occupation. Also, there are differences in housing pattern and significantly more forest resources are used in housing in the interior villages. For cooking, rarely people use charcoal, liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) and other cooking materials like kerosene and electricity. Though some families in Mawtawar use LPG gas or charcoal; in other villages, people use fuelwood for the non-availability of LPG.

Almost all the families in Mawlangkhar collect fuelwood. But in other three villages the figure varies from 45 to 62.5%, though most of the families in those villages use fuelwood or charcoal (Table 6). It indicates that several families in those villages purchase fuelwood, charcoal (of course that comes from

the nearby forests) from the market and many people earn their livelihoods by selling those. Family size is relatively smaller in Mawtawar and hence they have less manpower to collect fuel-wood from the relatively more degraded area and some of them have better job opportunities and therefore the opportunity cost of collecting fuel-wood is high.

Table 6: Distribution of Families as per the Collection of Forest Products (%)

Village	Fruit	Leaves	Fuelwood	Timber	Bamboo	Grass
Laitjem	0.00	5.00	50.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mawtawar	0.00	0.00	45.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
Sohiong	5.00	35.00	62.50	5.00	5.00	25.00
Mawlangkhar	15.00	52.50	97.50	20.00	10.00	60.00
Total	5.00	23.12	63.75	6.25	5.00	22.50

Source: Compiled from the field survey

Many of the people in the sample villages used to collect some other necessary items from the forests for meeting a part of their daily needs such as fruits, leaves, timber, bamboo, grass, etc. However, there is a significant variation in percentage of families collecting various forest products across the villages and the percentage is less in case of village that is located nearby the town.

Apart from those items, people of rural Meghalaya also collect wild roots, stems, bamboo shoots and seeds for consumption and some people also go for hunting. Wild biodiversity has been declining due to loss of dense forests. Though time series data is not available on those aspects, one can safely argue that the availability of those materials must be declining with the degradation of their host, which is forest.

There is a wide variation in average family, per capita income and expenditure of the households that collect forest materials (Table 7). In Laitjem, 21 out of 40 households collect materials from forest and have average family income of Rs. 3434.29. The figures for 17, 25 and 39 families of Mawtawar,

Sohiong and Mawlangkhar are Rs. 5910.88, Rs. 5818.84 and Rs. 3680.54, respectively.

Table 7: Monthly Average Income, Expenditure and Per Capita Income of the Households that collect materials from the Forests (Rs.)

Village	No. of HH	Population	Average family Income	Average Family Expenditure	Per Capita Income	Per Capita Expenditure
Laitjem	21	156	3434.29	3422.61	462.31	460.74
Mawtawar	17	106	5910.88	2952.00	947.97	473.43
Sohiong	25	200	5818.84	4052.88	727.36	506.61
Mawlangkhar	39	329	3680.54	3668.80	436.30	434.90

Note:
 HH means household.

Source: Compiled from the field survey.

Similarly, average family expenditure of those families varies from Rs 2952.00 to Rs. 4052.88. Per capita income in those villages varies from Rs. 462.31 to Rs 947.97, while per capita expenditure varies between Rs. 434.90 and Rs. 506.61. Except in Sohiong, other villages' per capita income and expenditure of the families who collect materials from forest are significantly lower than those, who do not collect anything from forest (comparing with Table 5). It indicates that the poorer are more dependent on forest for their survival.

Both permanent and shifting cultivation have been practiced by the villagers (Table 8). Rice is grown in the field especially by those practicing permanent cultivation, whereas in shifting cultivation, besides the main crops of rice and maize, other crops such as vegetables, millets, potatoes, sweet potatoes, pulses, chillies, ginger, cabbage, cauliflower and others are also grown.

Table 8 also shows that 30 and 35% of the cultivator families in Sohiong and Mawlangkhar, respectively follow both shifting and settled cultivation. Now many are following permanent cultivation due to lack of forest resources and that is

compounded with the rising population, though the productivity is still lower because of non-application of modern inputs. The none of these, here indicate the children or very old people of the cultivator headed families and those engaged in raising orchids, other plantations or in small business.

Table 8: Distribution of Family Members of the Cultivator Headed Families in the Sample Villages (%)

Village	Permanent (1)	Shifting (2)	Both (1&2)	None of these
Laitjem	20.00	17.50	22.50	40.00
Mawtawar	17.50	5.00	0.00	77.50
Sohiong	37.50	17.50	30.00	15.00
Mawlangkhar	55.00	0.00	35.00	10.00

Source: Compiled from the field survey

Table 9: Distribution of Families According to Ownership of Land (%)

Village	Own Land	Community Land	Other Private Land	Own & Other Private Land Both	Other Land
Laitjem	19.44	8.33	58.33	2.78	11.11
Mawtawar	2.78	22.22	69.44	5.56	00.00
Sohiong	16.22	32.43	48.65	2.70	00.00
Mawlangkhar	32.26	00.00	54.84	12.90	00.00

Source: Compiled from the field survey

Table 9 reveals that 19.44% of families in Laitjem have their own land for settled cultivation and rest of the people use community land (8.33%), other private individual land (58.33%). Only 2.78% of the families use both own and other private land. In Mawtawar, only 2.78% of the families own land, 22.22% use community land and 69.44% enjoy other private land and 5.56% use both types of land.

In Sohiong, 16.22% of the families have own land and 32.43% depend on the community land and 48.65% encroach other private individual land, whereas in Mawlangkhar 32.26% of

the people own land and 54.84% depend on other private land, 12.90% use both and there is no community land in this village. Based on the reply of the respondents, it was observed that in Laitjem there has been in-migration into the village during past 15 years (because it is nearer to town, despite being a poor village) from interior villages for business, cultivation or joining as daily labourers due to lack of sustenance in their native areas. The crisis in the migrants' original village has been due to population growth and simultaneous fall in availability of forest resource (Table 10).

Out-migration of the people in Mawtawar is nil and all the respondents agree that in-migration has been there from interior villages for opportunities in neighboring town and other reasons as mentioned above. Also 77.50% of the people in Sohiong agreed that the people from the village migrated to other parts of the state in search of job and employment opportunities and 85% of the respondents in Mawlangkhar informed about out-migration to urban areas for accessing better unskilled jobs. However, no immigration has been reported by the respondents of this village.

Some people of Sohiong and Mawlangkhar are reluctant to say anything about it. It indicates that the people of Mawlangkhar, who are very poor and due to large family size; intensity of dependence on forests increase, but earning from the forests have been declining due to degradation. Ultimately people have been forced to go to relatively developed or virgin forest areas for survival.

Table 10: Distribution of Families According to their Response on Migration within Past Fifteen Years due to forest related reasons (%)

Village	Out-migration	In-migration
Laitjem	2.50	97.50
Mawtawar	0.00	100.00
Sohiong	77.50	12.50
Mawlangkhar	85.00	0.00

Source: Compiled from the field survey

A comparison of tables reveals that people of poorer villages earn relatively more from forest. However, people of villages adjacent to towns or having more timber industries also harvest forest both for sustenance and commercial activities and hence intensify the process of degradation. Though major fuel sources in all the villages is firewood, in the distant villages intensity of fuel-wood use is relatively more due to lack of alternative energy resources. For the cultivation or harvesting of forest materials, people of all the villages depend both on personal, community and other private land.

Regression Results

Table 11: Two-Way Correlation Table

	Average Schooling	Monthly Family Income	Distance from Town	Land Ownership	Job Status	Family Size	No. of Saw Mill
Average Schooling	1	.0508	-.307	-.0556	-.516	-.105	.006
Monthly Family Income		1	-.1989	-.2752	.0785	-.539	-.071
Distance from Town			1	.0703	.2669	.142	00
Land Ownership				1	-	-.017	.020
Job Status					1	.091	-.029
Family Size						1	-
							.0158

Source: Compiled from the field survey.

Here simple linear regression is followed and though education, family size, job status is expected to be correlated, we find no significant correlation among them except between job status and education or family size and income (Table 11). Hence in some equations we exclude job status or consider only average schooling of the adults' only and record changes in parameters but no significant changes in result is observed.

The result indicates that there is a very insignificant impact of education on the collection of fuel-wood or percentage

of income earned from forest (Table 12). Actually, there is a high degree variation in educational level and a very few are educated in the sample villages. The incidence of poverty and lack of other opportunities push them towards forest resources and more so if it is common. Both, collection of fuel-wood and earning from forests are significantly positively affected by family size and negatively related to total family income. Better job opportunity is also negatively related to dependence of people on forest.

Table 12: Regression Results

Explanatory Variable	Dependent Variable					
	FW	INF	INF	INF	INF	INF
Const.	.332	.072	.120	.089	.078	.078
EDU	-.078 (-.67)	.017 (.82)	-.008 (.38)	-.0019 (-.208)	-.003 (-.31)	-.003 (-.31)
FI	-.0003 (-1.75)*	-.00012 (-4.13)**	-.00012 (-4.19)**	-.00012 (-4.43)**	-.00012 (-4.15)**	-.00012 (-4.15)**
FSIZE	.052 (3.76)**	.005 (2.03)**	.005 (2.02)**	.0043 (1.65)*	.0045 (1.61)*	.0045 (1.61)*
JOB	-.0313 (-1.077)**	-.009 (-1.75)*	-.0082 (-1.71)**			-.009 (-1.67)*
LAND	.174 (1.98)**	.0111 (.7192)	.011 (.75)	.011 (.754)	.0116 (.75)	.0116 (.75)
D	.183 (2.42)**	.064 (4.78)**	.0602 (4.81)**	.064 (5.15)**	.061 (4.56)**	.061 (4.56)**
SM			-.014 (-4.94)**	-.014 (-4.97)**		
R ²	0.29	0.32	0.41	0.39	0.33	0.33
N = 160			Incorporating the number of sawmills in the villages	Incorporating average schooling of adult members & leaving job status of head of the families	Considering job status of head of household & excluding number of sawmills	
<p>Note: {Here, FW represents fuel-wood, INF the percentage contribution of forest resources to family income, EDU the average year of schooling, FI the monthly family income, FSIZE means family size, JOB the job status, LAND the land ownership, D the distance of village from the nearest town, SM represents the presence of sawmill. Figures in the parentheses are the t-values, where * and ** indicate that the coefficient is significant at 10 and 5% level of significance respectively}. [For job status, we used 1 for service, 2 for agricultural labourer, 3 for cultivator, 4 for business and 5 for others. Normally it is assumed that better combined job status of families lowers the impact on degradation.]</p>						

Larger family size means more requirements and thus it intensifies harvesting of forest. Moreover, we have seen that low educated and relatively poor villagers have relatively larger family size and hence dependence is more. The negative coefficient of FI indicates that the affluent people will be less dependent on forest. It does not mean that they do not use forest resources.

What it indicates is that they devote less time for harvesting forest due to the high opportunity cost of their time. Rather they collect fuel-wood, charcoal and other items from the other people as in the interior villages LPG and other fuel is not available. Also, they find some locally collected items cheaper than at town and hence many of the items available in the nearby forests also find place in their daily menu, though the percentage is less for the rich.

Though from the overall sample villages we find an inverse relation between income and extraction of forest resources, in one village (Mawlangkhar), it was observed that average income of the people who extract forest is more than who do not. In that village (which is also far away from town/business centre) forest and agriculture together constitutes the main occupation due to lack of other opportunities. Hence those who collect more earn more.

Moreover, a very few people own land (31 family out of 160 in total) and thus they harvest commercially though on a limited scale. That is why the distance here has significantly positive impact on collection of fuel-wood and contribution of forest to family income. Though there is limited commercial activity, it is one of their main earning sources.

However, presence of saw-mills (some of which are closed now) have a negative impact on the percentage of earning from forests. Actually, saw-mills are run through large scale commercial extraction of timber, but that is of private forest of the owners in many cases or if it is a community forest, then it

provides revenue mainly to those who have better access and control over it. The general poor families extract mainly for survival.

Conclusion and Policy Implications

In conclusion it may be said that population growth, with poor technological and industrial progress in Meghalaya, cause significant rise in extraction of forest resources for sustenance. Inter-district variation in population growth and per capita NDDP was inversely correlated with the variation in population growth, while rural literacy rate is found to be insignificant.

Rising educational level is expected to raise the earning capacity, reduce demand for multiple children, and also raise awareness about the need for judicious use and preservation of forests. But mere variation in literacy is not enough if the area suffers from high degree of poverty. The poor people, even if lesser educated are expected to prefer more children for their future insurance and also to extract forest resources for survival where there is no other major source of sustenance (Goodstein, 1999). Poverty level in the state has not reduced significantly, as reflected from the low all-India ranking in poverty and human development.

Livelihood activities including collection of fuelwood and consumption items, cattle rearing is partly shaped by the availability of resources available in the neighboring forests. Also, earning of forest dwellers substantially dependent on the collection of timber, which gets expedited with open access and timber industry in the neighborhood. Even though the well-off families do not collect forest resources by themselves, they buy from the collectors for daily use at lower cost than the available substitutes. Collection of fuel-wood or other consumption items is positively associated with the family size, which is significant.

Though at the individual household level, rising income is inversely related to the degradation of forests, the more the contribution of forest, with other things remaining identical (technology, productivity of other sector), the faster is the NSDP growth. It means that the district that has higher potential for extraction of forest resource, observes better growth of income.

Although in general, rising income is supposed to be associated with the reduction in dependence on forests, in the interior villages without alternative opportunities except for farming and where forest is common, the income rises proportionately with extraction.

Conservation of forests and maintenance of sustainable livelihood of the people is contingent upon the building of human resources, technological development and an appropriate land use pattern maintaining the productivity of forest resources. Education and training teach how to manage resources scientifically, change livelihood patterns and lower the demand for children and thereby lead to population control and raise efficiency of forest resources for sustainable benefit.

Improved communication with the remote areas leads to enhancement of commercial extraction. Also, it may help in supply of alternative fuel to the interior areas, increase scope of education and healthcare opportunities to the people residing therein. However, the harvesting cannot be stopped as forest dwellers are heavily dependent upon forests. Instead, a scientific approach can be adopted to simultaneously obtain livelihood options to maintain the standard of local economy with a sustainable harvesting of forest resources.

References

- Aluko, M.A.O. 2004. "Sustainable Development, Environmental Degradation and the Entrenchment of Poverty in the Niger Delta of Nigeria," *Journal of Human Ecology: International, Interdisciplinary Journal of Man-Environment Relationship*, 15(1): 63-68.

- Anderson, P. 1989. "The Myth of Sustainable Logging: The Case for a Ban on Tropical Timber Imports," *The Ecologist*, 19(5): 166-168.
- Bhagat, R.B. and Hassan, Md. I. 1994. "On the Relationship between Population, Underdevelopment and Environment: Are we really in Malthusian Trap?" *The Indian Geographical Journal*, 69(2): 93-98.
- Birdsall, N. 1994. "Government, Population and Poverty: A Win-Win Tale," in Lindahl-Kiessling, K. and H. Landberg (eds.), *Population, Economic Development and the Environment*, Oxford University Press: 173-195.
- Boyce, J. K. 1994. "Inequality as a Cause of Environmental Degradation," *Ecological Economics*, 11(3): 169-178.
- Chauhan, I. S. and Chauhan, A. 1998. *Environmental Degradation*, Rawat Publications, Jaipur and New Delhi.
- Cropper M. and Griffiths, C. 1994. "The Interaction of Population Growth and Environmental Quality," *American Economic Review*, 84(2): 250-254.
- Cruz, W. and Gills, C. 1990. "Resource Policy Reform in the Context of Population Pressure: The Philippines and Nepal" in D. Chapman (ed.) *Arresting Renewable Resource Degradation in the Third World*, World Bank Environment Working Paper No. 44, Washington D. C.: The World Bank.
- Dasgupta, P., Folke, C. and Maler, K.G. 1994. "The Environmental Resource Base and Human Welfare," in Lindahl-Kiessling, K. and H. Landberg (eds.), *Population, Economic Development and Environment*, Oxford University Press: 25-50.
- Datta, S. (2000): "Population Growth and Natural Resource Base in Meghalaya," in B. Datta Ray (ed.), *Population, Poverty and Environment in North East India*, Concept Publishing Company, New Delhi: 173-182.
- De, U.K. 2003. "Economic Incentive and Environmental Management: A Study of Forestry in North-East India", in Z. Husain (ed.), *Environmental Issues of North East India*, Regency Publications, New Delhi: 170-188.
- De, U.K. 2004. "Human Resource Development and the Quality of Environment: Some Issues," presented in the National Seminar on Human Resource Development in North-East India, held in Agartala during September 18-19, 2004 and organized by Economic Science Society of Tripura in collaboration with State Resource Centre and Department of Analytical and Applied Economics, Tripura University.
- De, U.K. 2006. "Population, Poverty and The Problem of Natural Resource Management," Paper presented in the Conference on Demographic Dividend on 5-1-2006, organized by Liberty Institute, New Delhi.
- Dreze, J. and Sen, A. K. 1989. *Hunger and Public Action*, Clarendon Press, Oxford, London.
- Duraiappah, A. 1996. *Poverty and Environmental Degradation: Literature Review and Analysis*, CREED Working Paper Series, No 8. International Institute for Environment and Development, London.
- Dutta, R. 2000. "Ecological Degradation and Forest Resources in Meghalaya," in B. Datta Ray (ed.), *Population, Poverty and Environment in North East India*, Concept Publishing Company, New Delhi: 382-85.
- Ehrlich P. R. 1968. *The Population Bomb*, Sierra Club, Ballantine, New York.

- Ehrlich, A.R. and Ehrlich, P.R. 1990. *The Population Explosion*, New York, Simon and Schuster.
- Engelman, R. 1997. "Population as a Scale Factors: Impacts on Environment and Development," in R. K. Pachauri and Lubina F. Qureshy (eds.), *Population, Environment and Development*, Tata Energy Research Institute, New Delhi: 15-33.
- FAO. 1993. *Strategies for Sustainable Agriculture and Rural Development: The Role of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries*, Rome: UN Food and Agriculture Organization.
- Gill, M.S. 1999. "Population and Environment in District Leh (Ladakh), Jammu and Kashmir)," in *Population Geography – a Journal of the Association of Population Geographers of India*, 21(1 and 2): 19-30.
- Goodland, R. 1991. *Tropical Deforestation Solutions, Ethics and Religions*, World Bank Environment Working Paper, Washington D. C.: The World Bank.
- Goodstein, E.S. 1999. *Economics and the Environment*, 2nd edition, Chapter on Poverty, Population and the Environment, Prentice Hall, New Jersey: 429-460.
- Government of Meghalaya, Directorate of Economics and Statistics. 2017. *Statistical Handbook of Meghalaya*.
- Grossman and Krueger. 1995. "Economic Growth and the Environment," *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*: 353-377.
- Hardin, G. 1968. "The Tragedy of the Commons", *Science*, 162:124-48.
- Husain, Z. 1994. "Ecological Implications of Population Growth in North East India," in Sanu Mukherjee (ed), *Demographic Profile of North East India*, Omsons Publications, New Delhi:116-126.
- Ives, J. D. and Messerli, B. 1988. *The Himalayan Dilemma*, London: Routledge.
- Jaganathan, N.V. 1989. *Poverty, Public Policies and the Environment*, World Bank Environment Working Paper No. 24, Washington D.C.: The World Bank.
- Johnson, D.G. 2000. "Population, Food and Knowledge," *The American Economic Review*, 90(1): 1-14.
- Joshi, B.K. 1990. "Poverty, Inequality and the social Structure," in Tarlak Singh (Ed), *Social Science Research and Problem of Poverty*, Concept Publishing Company, New Delhi: 147.
- Kuri, P.K. 2005. *Common Property Resources, Environmental Externalities and Tribal Poverty in Arunachal Pradesh*, Unpublished UGC Sponsored Major Project Report, University of Burdwan.
- Macneill, J. 1989. "Strategies for Sustainable Economic Development," *Scientific American*, 261(3): 104-113.
- Malthus, T.R. (1798; 1992): *An Essay on the Principles of Population*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Meadow, D.H., Meadow, D.L., Randers, J and Behrens, W.W. 1972. *The Limits to Growth*, Universe Books, New York.
- Mink, S.D. 1993. "Poverty, Population and the Environment," World Bank Discussion Paper 189, The World Bank, Washington D.C.
- Neena, 2000. "Natural Resources Management for Sustainable Development (Land, Forests and Biodiversity)," in N. Rajalakshmi (ed.), *Environment and Economic Development*, Manak Publications, New Delhi: 284-294.

- Reidhead, P.W., Qureshy, L.F. and Narian, V. 1997. "Population, Environment and Development: Interactions and Issues," in R.K. Pachauri and L.F. Qureshy (eds.), *Population, Environment and Development*, Tata Energy Research Institute, New Delhi: 45-61.
- Repetto, R. 1990. "Deforestation in the Tropics," *Scientific American*, 262(4): 36-45.
- Sanchez, F.M. 1998. "Linkage between Poverty and Environmental Degradation- A Profound Opinion," in H. S. Sharma and S. Chattopadhyay (eds.), *Sustainable Development - Issues and Case Studies*, Concept Publishing Company, New Delhi.
- Sen, A.K. 1994. "Population and Research: Food, Fertility and Economic Development," in Lindahl-Kiessling, K. and H. Landberg (eds.), *Population, Economic Development and Environment*, Oxford University Press: 51-74.
- Simon, J. 1981. *The Ultimate Resource*, Princeton University Press, Princeton, USA.
- Simon, J. 1996. *The Ultimate Resource 2*, 2nd Edition, Princeton University Press, Princeton, USA.
- Simon, J. and Myers, N. 1994. *Scarcity or Abundance? A Debate on the Environment*, Norton, New York.
- Singh, B.P. 1987. *The Problem of Change: A Study of North East India*, Oxford University Press, New Delhi.
- Somanathan, E. 1991. "Deforestation, Property Rights and Incentives in Central Himalayas," *Economic and Political Weekly*, 26(4): PE37-PE46.
- Southgate, D. 1988. *The Economics of Land Degradation in the Third World*, World Bank Environment Working Paper No. 2, Washington D.C.: The World Bank.

ⁱ It came out during the discussion of the author with some District Council Members in East and West Khasi Hills Districts.